

Set of 40 studies of different patients

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Contact info.: <https://chameleon.eu/#contact>

Studies count: 40

Subjects count: 40

Age range: Between 52 years and 84 years

Sex: Male

Body part(s): PROSTATE, ARM, PELVIS, HEAD, Unknown

Modality: MR